

Real time monitoring of glucose in whole blood by smartphone

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Abstract

A combined thread-paper microfluidic device (μ TPAD) is presented for the determination of glucose in blood. The device is designed to include all the analytical operations needed: red blood cell separation, conditioning, enzymatic recognition, and colorimetric transduction. The signal is captured with a smartphone or tablet working in video mode and processed by custom Android-based software in real-time. The automatic detection of the region of interest on the thread allows for the use of either initial rate or equilibrium signal as analytical parameters. The time needed for analysis is 12 s using initial rate, and 100 s using the equilibrium measurement with a LOD of 48 μ M and 12 μ M, respectively, and a precision around 7%. The μ TPAD allows a rapid determination of glucose in real samples using only 3 μ L of whole blood.

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Keywords: Thread-paper microfluidic device; Glucose determination; Whole blood; Reaction rate; Smartphone.

41 **1. Introduction**

42 In our global society there is a drive to move the acquisition of chemical information from
43 the controlled environments of labs to the place where the information is needed. This
44 necessitates changing the methods used to generate analytical information from
45 approaches that are instrument and lab centered, to decentralized user-centered
46 approaches, the so-called distributed approaches (Hoekstra et al., 2018). One type of
47 analytical system that has the potential to provide fast, laboratory-quality results is lab-
48 on-a-chip devices that rely on microfluidic platforms allowing the miniaturization of
49 chemical assays (Mark et al., 2010). The use of capillarity as a liquid propulsion principle
50 presents advantages over other more complex propulsion systems in terms of simplicity,
51 low cost, biocompatibility, fast response, and user-friendly format. The development of
52 devices based mainly on paper, thread, and cloth have evolved into an active research
53 field with an increasing number of publications and reviews (Akyazi et al.,
54 2018;Aydingogan et al., 2018;Farajikhah et al., 2019;Hoekstra et al., 2018;Li and Steckl,
55 2018).

56 In combination with consumer electronic devices that include color sensors, mainly
57 smartphones and tablets, capillary-based devices have the potential to become a total
58 analytical system. These total analytical systems must be considered as a whole and
59 include everything needed to perform the analysis: sampling, sample treatment,
60 conditioning, analyte recognition, measurements, electronic equipment, and data
61 processing. They should operate in the most robust and simple way possible. These
62 systems do not produce data, but information relevant to the user in an understandable
63 format.

64 The use of thread brings various advantages for the manufacture of analytical devices in
65 terms of definition of path, strength, varied materials, and small volume of samples
66 (Nilghaz et al., 2013). Thread has been used as support for the manufacture of
67 microfluidic devices (μ TAD) that can implement various analytical operations, such as
68 support for recognition (Wu et al., 2016) and transduction reactions (Liu et al., 2017),
69 immobilization of reagents (Galpothdeniya et al., 2014), chromatographic (Agustini et
70 al., 2018) or electrophoretic (Cabot et al., 2018) separations, control and manipulation of
71 flow (Ballerini et al., 2011;Li et al., 2018) or sample conditioning (Ulum et al., 2016).
72 The measurement techniques are mainly optical and electrochemical, by integrating
73 electrodes onto the thread (Malon et al., 2017). The most commonly used optical
74 measurements, apart from the visual ones, are based on the acquisition of images from

75 the device with a scanner (Mao et al., 2015) or with a smartphone (Erenas et al., 2016)
76 and subsequent processing.

77 A variant in the design of microfluidic devices consists of the combination of thread and
78 paper which gives rise to the so-called microfluidic thread-paper based analytical device
79 (μ TPAD). These devices developed mainly by the team of Prof. F.A. Gómez, combine
80 the good conduction of fluids by the thread with the recognition process and the
81 subsequent acquisition of the color information from an image of a paper area obtained
82 with a scanner. They have been used for the enzymatic determination of glucose using a
83 three-channel system made with nylon thread and three reaction areas of chromatographic
84 paper (Gonzalez et al., 2016; Lee et al., 2018). Other systems described include a 3D
85 multilayered paper μ TPAD for the determination of glucose and BSA (Neris et al., 2019)
86 and two ELISA for biotinylated goat anti-mouse IgG and rabbit IgG (Gonzalez et al.,
87 2018a; Gonzalez et al., 2018b). Sateanchok et al. (Sateanchok et al., 2018) describes a
88 μ TPAD together with a smartphone for the total phenolic content in green tea using a
89 thread portion for the handling of samples and a paper portion for reaction with
90 immobilized reagents.

91 In this paper we consider the acquisition of the color information of the microfluidic
92 device through a smartphone working in video mode. This opens the door to use kinetic
93 measures to obtain analytical information, which can significantly shorten the analysis
94 time. Additionally, the determination of glucose in whole blood requires separating the
95 red blood cell (RBC) from the plasma, which is achieved with an μ TPAD incorporating
96 a separation membrane. Blood samples collected from volunteers were analyzed with
97 μ TPAD as well as with a portable glucose meter, in order to validate results.

98

99 **EXPERIMENTAL METHODS**

100 **Materials and Equipment.** The thread used as support for the μ TPAD preparation was
101 a commercial white cotton thread (caliber 12 and N_{Tex} 94) from Finca (Presencia
102 Hilaturas S.A. Alzira, Valencia, Spain) measuring around 600 μ m in diameter and
103 containing 250 ± 10 fibers (Erenas et al., 2016). The reagents included on the thread were
104 3,3',5,5'-tetramethylbenzidine (TMB), glucose oxidase from *Aspergillus Niger* (GOx),
105 horseradish peroxidase (HRP), chitosan, β -D-glucose, and phosphate buffer solution
106 (1xPBS) containing NaCl, KCl, Na₂HPO₄ and KH₂PO₄. All these reagents were
107 purchased from Sigma Aldrich (Sigma–Aldrich Quimica S.A., Madrid, Spain). Acetic
108 acid, ethanol, and hydrogen peroxide were purchased from Panreac S.A. (Barcelona,

109 Spain). Reverse osmosis type quality water (Milli-RO 12 plus Milli-Q station (Millipore,
110 Bedford, MA, U.S.), conductivity 18.2 M Ω ·cm) was used throughout. Whole blood
111 separation membranes MF1, LF1, VF2 and GF/DVA were used and purchased from
112 Whatman (Little Chalfont, Buckinghamshire, United Kingdom).

113 All the blood samples were obtained from healthy volunteers and collected in tubes
114 containing EDTA to avoid the clotting of samples. Once the blood samples were extracted
115 they were preserved at 4°C for up to one week.

116 The μ TAD images were recorded and processed using a variety of devices including a
117 Sony DSC-HX300 digital camera (Sony, Tokyo, Japan), a Samsung Galaxy S5
118 smartphone, a Samsung Galaxy Tab A tablet (Samsung Electronics, Suwon, South
119 Korea), and a Motorola Moto G4 Play smartphone (Lenovo Goup LTD, Beijing, China).
120 ImageJ software (National Institutes of Health, Bethesda, Maryland, USA) with the Color
121 Space Converter plugin (<http://rsb.info.nih.gov/ij/plugins/color-space-converter.html>)
122 was used to analyze digital images. Avidemux 2.6 (Mean) was used to obtain single
123 frames from video files for analysis by ImageJ. The Anaconda distribution of Python
124 (Continuum Analytics), OpenCV (Open Source Computer Vision), and Android Studio
125 (Google) were used for the development of application software for the processing of
126 video files and for the real-time Android app.

127 The laboratory evaluations of glucose μ TAD in whole blood and plasma samples were
128 completed for validation purposes using an Accu-Chek Aviva Nano glucose meter
129 (Roche, Switzerland) provided with test-strips.

130

131 **Thread-based device preparation**

132 The outer waxy layer of cotton thread, called cuticle, confers hydrophobic properties
133 which affects the wicking and wetting properties. To remove this layer, the thread is
134 scoured in a boiling solution of 10 mg/mL Na₂CO₃ for 5 minutes (Nilghaz and Shen,
135 2015). Afterwards, the thread is washed several times until the rinsate has a neutral pH,
136 sonicated 3 times in purified water for 5 minutes, allowed to dry at room temperature, and
137 stored in a closed container for further use.

138 The basic design of the μ TAD for glucose determination is shown in Figure 1i. It consists
139 of a 2.5 cm-long thread attached to a piece of double-sided adhesive tape with three
140 different regions: A) a sampling region where sample is placed; B) a recognition region
141 where GOx is retained and H₂O₂ produced; and C) a transduction region where TMB is
142 oxidized changing the color of thread. To prepare the device, 5.0 μ L of 1xPBS is added

143 in the sampling region and allowed to dry for two minutes. Then 1.0 μL of 1.74 U/ μL
144 GOx is added in the recognition region followed by 0.35 μL of 20.8 mM TMB in ethanol,
145 0.35 μL of $3.5 \cdot 10^{-2}$ U/mL HRP, and, after waiting one minute, 0.7 μL of a 1 mg/mL
146 chitosan aqueous solution is added to the transduction region. The device is then left to
147 dry at room temperature for a few minutes. The devices are kept in the darkness until use.

148 Figure 1

149 For whole blood glucose determination, the μTAD preparation was modified for the small
150 volume of serum produced (Figure 1ii). To a 1.5 cm-long piece of thread 2.5 μL of 1xPBS
151 is added to the sampling region and allowed to dry at room temperature for 10 minutes.
152 Then 0.5 μL of a solution containing $2.8 \cdot 10^{-2}$ U/mL HRP, 3.48 U/mL GOx, 0.5 μL of
153 14.56 mM TMB in ethanol, and 0.7 μL of 1 mg/mL chitosan in water is deposited in the
154 recognition and transduction region. Finally, a 4 mm x 5 mm diameter tear-shaped piece
155 of LF1 whole blood separation membrane was placed at the beginning of sampling region
156 of thread.

157 In order to use the μTAD for whole blood glucose determination we designed a two-piece
158 methacrylate custom case (Figure 1iii) that holds the thread in a channel engraved for this
159 purpose and allows the acquisition of video with the smartphone. The case was designed
160 using Illustrator software and engraved using a Rayjet Trotec Laser engraving printer
161 (Trotec, Austria) using Rayjet Commander software. A thread and separation membrane
162 are placed on the groove in the bottom piece, and the top, that has two holes for sampling
163 and recording the video, is placed over it, and the μTAD is ready for use.

164

165 **μTAD image capture and processing**

166 The digital images were captured using a Sony DSC-HX300 digital camera and Motorola
167 Moto G⁴ Play smartphone. For still images the camera was set-up as follows: resolution
168 of 3648x2736 pixels, aperture value f/3.5, exposure time 1/40 s, ISO-80, 2800K white
169 balance (see Figure S1), and images were saved in jpg format (Joint Photographic Experts
170 Group). For video recordings the camera was set-up as follows: resolution of 1440x1080
171 pixels, 25 frames per second, and 2800K white balance, and the files were saved in MTS
172 (AVCHD) format. All the images were captured inside a custom cubic light box
173 illuminated by two LED light bulbs (3000K) located in a fixed position. Image and video
174 files from the μTAD were analyzed using ImageJ and the in-house app. All the
175 optimization related to the μTAD and μTPAD , was performed using the Sony digital

176 camera to image the device. Calibration and validation of the device was performed using
177 Motorola Moto G⁴ Play smartphone and the custom Android app.

178

179 **Developed software for image-processing**

180 The basic steps employed in the custom image processing software are outlined here, and
181 a more detailed description is given in the supplementary information. The image is first
182 transformed from the RGB color space to the HSV color space. The hue channel is used
183 to identify the type of pixel (e.g. red pixels are whole blood; blue pixels are chemically
184 active areas of the thread), and the saturation channel is used to identify the region of
185 interest and track the degree of color development. An additional set of values, the color
186 absorbance ratios, are also calculated. These three values, hereafter referred to as cA123,
187 are defined as the negative log of the ratio of two RGB channels. For example, cA1 is
188 the $-\log(\text{Blue}/\text{Green})$ (Cantrell et al., 2010). A single region of interest (ROI) was
189 automatically identified as the largest contiguous group of colored pixels. Pixels are
190 masked as colored if their saturation is greater than a threshold amount (≥ 40 in an 8-bit
191 image). Only pixels inside this ROI are used in subsequent data manipulations. For
192 pixels in the ROI, the mean, median, and standard deviation are calculated for RGB, HSV,
193 and cA123, and a histogram of the individual values is displayed on the screen and
194 recorded in a text file along with the elapsed time for that frame. A subset of the data from
195 12 seconds before the elapsed time up to and including the current frame is defined. A
196 least-squares linear fit to the analytical parameter versus time within the 12s window is
197 then calculated. The slope of this line is taken to be the rate of change in the device
198 response. Both the moving average of the analytical parameter and the rate of change are
199 displayed as separate auto-scaling plots. The raw video, processed video, and summary
200 data for each frame are each stored as separate files. The Android-based application was
201 developed and tested using two different Samsung devices. The final calibration and
202 validation of the μ TPAD was done with a lower processing capacity Motorola Moto G⁴
203 Play smartphone.

204

205 **Calibration and validation of μ TAD and μ TPAD**

206 In order to use the μ TPAD, 3 μ L of whole blood sample was deposited on the sampling
207 area, and a Motorola Moto G⁴ Play smartphone running the Android-based app was used
208 to monitor the color change. To validate the results, the concentrations obtained were
209 compared to a commercial glucometer (Accu-Check) together with the glucose test strips.

210 The test-strip is introduced in the glucometer, and 0.6 μL of whole blood is placed on the
211 sampling area to measure the glucose concentration with the glucometer. Each whole
212 blood sample was analyzed 3 times using the glucometer and results obtained compared
213 to the provided by the μTPAD in terms of percent error.

214

215 **RESULTS AND DISCUSSION**

216 Thread is a potential substrate for microfluidic devices fabrication with some advantages
217 compared to paper such as high mechanical strength (both in dry and wet conditions),
218 flexibility, lightweight, and ease of functionalization. A large variety of materials with
219 different properties are available, and the thread itself is the driving channel, contrary to
220 what happens in paper in which the channel must be defined (Malon et al., 2017; Nilghaz
221 et al., 2013). A very common substrate is cotton, a super-hydrophilic material, whose
222 specific properties depend on chemical composition and surface morphology (Darmanin
223 and Guittard, 2014). In this application, the gaps intra-yarn, inter-yarn, and lumen of each
224 fiber account for the capillary action by wicking the liquid into the thread (Banerjee et
225 al., 2013). We selected commercial cotton thread ($\sim 600 \mu$ diameter and 250 ± 10 fibers) as
226 the material for the capillary platform combined with paper to implement all analytical
227 operations: particles separation, fluid transport, chemistry immobilization and
228 colorimetric transduction. The capillary movement of water in the selected thread shows
229 minor deviation from Washburn-type behavior ($L = a\sqrt{t}$; $a = 0.8185 \pm 0.0065$). The μTAD
230 designed for glucose determination is a single-channel device with a sampling area on
231 one end of the thread and a detection area containing the recognition chemistry at the
232 other end. The principle of the dry-reagent cotton thread-based assay is based on
233 enzymatic oxidation of glucose using GOx/HRP and colorimetric transduction with
234 TMB.

235

236 **μTAD optimization**

237 To adjust the enzymatic solution method to the μTAD format, different variables were
238 studied and optimized (additional details are given in the supplementary information).
239 For the transduction reactions the on-thread TMB immobilization, the amount of TMB
240 and HRP, and the pH adjustment were all optimized. For the recognition reactions the
241 amount of GOx and volume of sample added were studied. TMB is the reagent selected
242 for the optical transduction of the enzymatically generated H_2O_2 . TMB is insoluble in

243 water, but the blue oxidation product is soluble and can be dragged through the medium
244 by the sample. Chitosan is used to preconcentrate the oxidized TMB in the detection area
245 as it is strongly retained to paper (Ariza-Avidad et al., 2016; Gabriel et al., 2016) and
246 cloth-based devices (Bagherbaigi et al., 2014). It slows the movement of the oxidized
247 TMB and increases the homogeneity of the ROI (Liu et al., 2014). The deposition of 0.7
248 μg of chitosan (0.7 μl of 1 mg/mL solution) reduces the length of TMB oxidized area
249 (16%) and improves reproducibility (from 20.3% CV without chitosan to 3.6% with it,
250 $n=3$) (Table S1).

251 As TMB and HRP mutually influence one another, their optimization was performed
252 simultaneously by a factorial design obtaining a maximum saturation signal for 14.0 μU
253 and $7.3 \cdot 10^{-3}$ μmol of HRP and TMB, respectively (Figure S3). The immobilization by
254 drying of pH 7.4 PBS buffer in the thread improves the precision (7.6% compared to
255 11.5%) and simplifies the use of the device, thus we included the buffer in the μTAD
256 although it reduces the equilibrium value of the saturation signal (Figure S4).

257 To study the GOx dependence, different concentrations were deposited on the thread and
258 the evolution of saturation signal was monitored over time (Figure S5). The largest
259 saturations were obtained with 1.74 U of GOx. Interestingly a substantial lowering in the
260 reaction time for equilibration (100 s) was observed, which is a much lower time than
261 described in literature, typically around 10 min (Table S3).

262 The maximum saturation signal was obtained for 10 μL samples. For smaller volumes,
263 the signal decreases because a smaller amount of glucose is present, and the precision is
264 lower due to the thread not being completely wet (Figure S6). Alternatively, at higher
265 sample volumes the oxidized TMB is dragged from ROI, decreasing the signal and
266 lowering the precision.

267

268 **μTAD analytical characterization**

269 To study the performance of the system we prepared 10 different glucose standards, five
270 replicates each, using 50 different μTAD devices (each is a one-use device) while
271 recording the evolution of colors with a smartphone in real-time using the custom Android
272 app. As analytical parameters we studied both the initial reaction rate using a window of
273 12 s from the time when the app detects a change on the color of thread (Figure 2) and
274 the equilibrium signal measured as the saturation 100 seconds after the sample addition
275 (Figure S7). In both cases, the relationship between the logarithm of glucose

276 concentration and the analytical parameter is sigmoidal and is fitted to a Boltzmann
277 equation (Equation 1).

278

$$279 \quad y = A_2 + \frac{(A_1 - A_2)}{1 + e^{-\frac{(x - A_3)}{A_4}}} \quad \text{Eq. 1}$$

280

Figure 2

281 Analytical figures of merit obtained using both methods (rate based and equilibrium) are
282 shown in Table 1. The limit of detection was calculated as 6 times the standard deviation
283 of the blank (Mistberger et al., 2014), obtaining a value of 48 μM for initial rate and 12
284 μM when equilibrium saturation is used. These values are much lower than those in the
285 literature for colorimetric μPAD 's for glucose (Chun et al., 2014; Gabriel et al.,
286 2017; Gonzalez et al., 2016) and comparable to those obtained by a bipolar ECL thread-
287 based method (Liu et al., 2017) (Table S3). A precision study was also performed at three
288 different concentrations, 10 replicates each, obtaining values ranging from 5.5% to 7.8%.
289 Although an analysis time of 100 seconds is a major improvement for colorimetric
290 devices compared with literature (Ariza-Avidad et al., 2016; Gabriel et al., 2017; Zhu et
291 al., 2017), the use of initial rate measured in real-time further reduces the analysis time
292 down to 12 seconds. A study of the stability of μTAD over time in two different
293 preservation conditions, fridge and desiccator, showed short lifetimes (Figure S8) as is
294 typical for these systems (Zhu et al., 2017).

295

Table 1

296 **Glucose determination in whole blood**

297 To perform the conventional spectrophotometric determination of glucose in blood in the
298 laboratory, it is necessary to separate plasma from the RBC via centrifugation, to avoid
299 their interference in the blue color of oxidized TMB (Li and Steckl, 2018). In order to
300 meet the ASSURED guidelines (Mabey et al., 2004), we studied the inclusion of an RBC
301 separation step in the developed μTAD while keeping the device as small as possible.

302 Different strategies have been described in literature to integrate RBC separation from
303 plasma in paper and thread devices. Some are based on the use of different salts in the
304 thread to induce blood clotting, such as NaCl (Nilghaz and Shen, 2015; Yan et al., 2014)
305 or CaCl_2 (Li et al., 2014); anticoagulants such as EDTA (Ulum et al., 2016); agglutinating
306 antibodies (Al-Tamimi et al., 2012; Yang and Lin, 2015) or paper membranes (Songjaroen
307 et al., 2012).

308 The use of NaCl or EDTA in different conditions of concentration and temperature did
309 not result in appreciable separation of plasma in the small volumes of blood used (see SI
310 3.8). Blood filter paper (Songjaroen et al., 2012) is used to separate the RBC from whole
311 blood by trapping them on the membrane while allowing plasma to flow by capillarity to
312 the recognition area. As paper filters to remove particles greater than 2–3 μm , we tested
313 polyvinyl alcohol-bound glass fiber membranes (MF1, LF1 and VF2) and binder-free
314 glass fiber membrane (VF1). To test filter papers, a 6 mm round shape membrane was
315 located at the beginning of the μTAD and 10 μL of whole blood was used. Only LF1
316 paper provided a sufficient amount of plasma for samples this small.

317 To reduce the blood volume needed, we designed a tear shape membrane connected to
318 the thread by the tip (Figure 1ii) and tested different tear sizes and blood volumes. We
319 selected a 4 mm x 5 mm diameter tear-shaped membrane and 3 μL of blood. Figure 3
320 shows the plot-line saturation profiles of the device with 3 μL and 4 μL of blood. A sharp
321 change in saturation is observed for the 3 μL sample size indicating better RBC separation
322 than the progressive increase seen in the 4 μL sample size.

323 Figure 3

324 Due to the low volume of plasma obtained from 3 μL of whole blood, it was necessary to
325 redesign the device to overlap the recognition and detection areas (Figure 1ii).
326 Consequently, we designed a combined thread – paper microfluidic device, a μTPAD , to
327 include the different analytical operations needed for glucose analysis in total blood: RBC
328 separation, conditioning, recognition, and transduction.

329 For ease the use, we designed a custom casing in two-piece methacrylate. The bottom is
330 engraved with a slit that allows lodging both the thread and the membrane in a fixed
331 position. The top has two holes for sampling and collecting the signal with the smartphone
332 (Figure S4). This housing was designed to fulfill the ASSURED guidelines of user-
333 friendly operation and safety; the user cannot touch the sampling area or thread where the
334 reaction will occur.

335 To calibrate the μTPAD a series of whole blood samples with known amounts of glucose
336 around physiological levels were prepared. A 50 μL aliquot of whole blood was left at
337 room temperature for 6 hours so that glycolysis consumes the glucose present, and it was
338 then spiked with 0.5 μL of a glucose standard. The calibration function is shown in Figure
339 4, and the details of the fit to linear equation and figures of merit are presented in Table
340 1. Due to the rapid change in color of the μTPAD when a whole blood sample is analyzed,
341 it is not possible to use the initial rate as analytical parameter.

342
343 A precision study was carried out at 50.0, 90.0 and 110.0 mg/dL of glucose, with 10
344 replicates per solution. Relative standard deviations of 6.6%, 6.9% and 5.2%,
345 respectively, were measured. Taking into account that the precision of the colorimetric
346 method in a laboratory is around 5% (Burtis and Bruns, 2007), the values obtained with
347 this device are quite acceptable. This complete system not only measures the glucose
348 concentration, but it also separates plasma from whole blood and performs multiple
349 buffered reactions without any manipulation of sample. Finally, the price of a sensor was
350 estimated to be 0.0087 €/μTPAD without the case and 0.0999 €/μTPAD including it.
351 (Table S2).

352 Once the development and optimization of the different variables were performed, the
353 μTPAD was applied to real whole blood samples supplied from seven different healthy
354 volunteers. In all cases, 3 μL of blood was added to the μTAD without any kind of
355 previous treatment. The measured values range from 3% to 17% (Table 2) percent error
356 when compared to a commercial glucose meter.

357

358 **Conclusions**

359

360 A microfluidic single-channel device that combines hydrophilic cotton thread and paper
361 is described for the determination of glucose in total blood. The assay is based on the
362 immobilization of all reagents needed for the enzymatic oxidation of glucose and
363 colorimetric transduction with TMB. This design allows for very short equilibration
364 times, as low as 100 s, due to the high surface area of the thread. The change in color is
365 measured with a smartphone working in video mode and processed with a custom
366 Android-based app capable of the automatic detection of the region of interest on the
367 thread. This makes it possible to obtain color information in real-time and process it to
368 obtain both reaction rate and equilibrium signal. The rate-based analysis time is as low as
369 12 s. To the best of our knowledge, this is the first described kinetic analysis for a
370 capillary-based microfluidic device. For glucose determination in whole blood, we have
371 combined the thread with a glass fiber membrane for plasma separation. This μTPAD
372 was used to successfully determine glucose directly using only 3 μL of blood drawn from
373 healthy volunteers. The development of this technology that combines different capillary
374 materials and the use of kinetic signals obtained with smartphone is a significant step
375 forward in terms inexpensive, portable, rapid, and user-friendly chemical analysis.

376

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Table 1. Calibration function and analytical parameter of the method when saturation and initial rate are used as analytical parameter.

Calibration function (Initial rate)		Calibration function (Saturation)		Calibration function (Total blood)	
A1	-0.006	A1	0.164		
A2	3.352	A2	0.776	Intercept	5.344
A3	2.666	A3	2.403	Slope	0.257
A4	0.320	A4	0.490		
R ²	0.987	R ²	0.966	R ²	0.991
LOD	48 μ M	LOD	12 μ M	LOD	28 mg/dL
Analysis time	12 s	Analysis time	100 s	Analysis time	~10 s
Precision					
15 μ M	10.2 %	15 μ M	7.8 %	50 mg/dL	6.6%
125 μ M	5.7 %	125 μ M	7.2 %	90 mg/dL	6.9 %
500 μ M	9.1 %	500 μ M	5.5 %	110 mg/dL	5.2 %

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Table 2. Validation of whole blood samples using the μ TPAD and a commercial glucose meter as reference method.

Whole blood sample	Glucose meter	μ TPAD	Error
1	65 mg/dL	67 mg/dL	3%
2	66 mg/dL	72 mg/dL	10%
3	51 mg/dL	60 mg/dL	17%
4	65 mg/dL	59 mg/dL	10%
5	73 mg/dL	75 mg/dL	3%
6	119 mg/dL	113 mg/dL	5%
7	67 mg/dL	79 mg/dL	4%

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528 **Figures**

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531 **Figure 1.** i) Picture of the μ TAD for glucose: A) Sampling region; B) detection region;
532 C) transduction region. ii) Picture of μ TPAD for whole blood glucose: D) RBC paper
533 based separation membrane and sampling area; E) detection and transduction area. iii)
534 Case designed to contain the μ TPAD with a hole for blood sampling and a window for
535 video recording.

536 **Figure 2.** Calibration of μ TAD sensing membrane using initial rate and adjust to a
537 Boltzmann equation

538 **Figure 3.** Saturation plot profile of the device when different volumes of 3 and 4 μ L of
539 whole blood sample are added. i) 3 μ L; ii) 4 μ L

540 **Figure 4.** Calibration of μ TAD obtained from whole blood spiked samples

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Figure 1

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Figure 2

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Figure 3

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Figure 4